

Project details

Subsidy basis

Partner	Funding rules	
OPEN LIFE SCIENCE LIMITED (Lead)	Subsidy control	View answers

Application team

OPEN LIFE SCIENCE LIMITED

Organisation details

Type	Business

Team members

Full name	Email	EDI survey
Yo Yehudi	yo@we-are-ols.org	Complete
Bethan Iley	bethan@we-are-ols.org	Complete

Application details

Competition name

Women in Innovation Award 2024/25

Application name

The Greenhouse: Incubating change-makers and spin-outs for academia-industry collaborations

When do you wish to start your project?

1 December 2024

Project duration in months

12 months

Innovation area

Emerging technology

Has this application been previously submitted to Innovate UK?

No

Application location

Applicant location

31 Eaton Estate

Wimblington

PE15 0QE

Public description

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Scientists regularly create new knowledge: whether groundbreaking innovative ways of doing things we'd never considered before, better understanding of concepts we already observed, or incremental improvements on real challenges. Whilst scientists are highly trained individuals, however, many do not have experience sharing their work with others (the only way true innovation can happen, arguably, is by allowing others to build upon your work). **Most scientists also aren't entrepreneurs: the idea of doing scientific work independently outside of the ivory tower is intimidating.**

As Executive Director of OLS, I run an organisation dedicated to creating diverse and equitable open science. We have been running open science training since 2019, and built a community of 600+ individuals worldwide. This grant will allow us to "level up" our work, supporting other scientists to spin out their own open science initiatives outside academia, in ways relevant in their own settings, as well as documenting our playbook so anyone can pick it up if they wish.

Essentially, **rather than giving a man a fish, or even teaching a man to fish** (or perhaps a woman, given this grant's focus!), **we instead will create a guide for scientists to "start their own fishery"**, creating an openly shared blueprint for "spinning out" successful academia-to-industry open science initiatives. Whilst university patent offices and technology transfer programs exist, we're not aware of any open-science oriented spin-out guides on the market, oriented towards scientists who wish to share their work out of passion rather than a desire for profit.

Success of this project will be measured by the following three outcomes:

- **Blueprint:** a step-by-step guide for setting up your own UK-based open

research-oriented initiative outside a university.

- **Training:** Delivering open science training to 5-10 scientists, including trialling the blueprint at a partner university and iterating based on feedback.
- **Scoping 2-3 potential new contracts** to create the same "multiplier effect" partnership at other institutes - this time as a service, based on the now-proven model funded by this project. This will be an essential part of our activities that we hope will be enabled by the support package this Innovate UK offers for this grant.

Scope

Scope

This competition focuses on supporting role-models in business and innovation. As an entrepreneur leading a humanitarian-oriented business that has successfully operated for several years, and a **scientist with a doctorate in Computer Science**, I believe I fit this role well. I'm especially proud of **winning a grant from NASA in 2023** to deliver open science training over the next three years.

I am also **relatable**: I'm no precocious Richard Branson buying my own island at age 28. Instead, I'm nearly 40, an immigrant born outside the UK, and a highschool dropout who got married at the age of 18. I could not afford to go to university full time in my teens and early 20s - instead I worked full-time sending faxes for the NHS. I completed my Bachelors over a period of nine years via the Open University - and by the time I graduated, I worked at the University of Cambridge as a Software Engineer. My personal example shows that **grit and tenacity** helps you succeed, perhaps more than where you come from, or what fancy university you attended.

I also wouldn't be where I am today without my team of co-directors, employees, contractors, and the wider community: together we have a shared vision of enabling more science, and better science, by sharing our innovations widely and teaching others how to do the same. Together we've built a community for over 600 people in all continents except Antarctica, and brought open science training to 55+ countries worldwide.

If this grant were to be awarded, I would look forward to supporting my colleagues to create blueprints to enable open science industry-academia collaboration. But I'll be even more excited in the future, after the grant has ended, if we can find enough support from industry to incubate Open Science fellows who go on to launch their own open science businesses, and no longer rely on our support and coaching.

I believe in a future where scientists routinely share their innovations freely with the world so that others can benefit from them, where "business" isn't a

synonym for "failure" to scientists, and **where more scientists and entrepreneurs look like me**: a highschool dropout, or an immigrant, a woman who got married young, or someone who didn't have it all on a silver spoon.

Application questions

1. Minimal Financial Assistance declaration (not scored)

Minimal Financial Assistance Declaration (not scored)

See attached

Uploaded MFA Declaration - UKRI.pdf

[MFA Declaration - UKRI.pdf \(opens in a new window\) \(/application/10135254/form/question/40904/forminput/113411/file/726187/download\).](/application/10135254/form/question/40904/forminput/113411/file/726187/download)

2. Animal Testing (not scored)

Will your project involve any trials with animals or animal testing?

No

3. Role Model Commitment (not scored)

Can you commit five days over the duration of the award to activities related to being a role model?

Yes, I am available for five days.

As a computer scientist with a doctoral degree, I believe role models are incredibly important. My own journey illustrates this - I was in my 30s before it even occurred to me that I might want to become a scientist, and the only reason I considered it was because I had met several other people with PhDs. To my surprise, these people weren't "crazy smart" - they were actually just people, similar to me. This opened my eyes in a way I'd never considered before - could I - a highschool dropout - do science too? And then of course I "accidentally" co-founded a small business while I was studying for my doctorate, too. I'd like to see more young women getting into computer science and entrepreneurship - and to learn that it's not nearly as terrifying or hostile as it might seem.

4. Further Business Support (not scored)

Further Business Support (not scored)

Yes

5. Video

You must provide a video to describe your proposal.

https://youtu.be/WArq7_D7TKk

6. Need or challenge

What pressing societal, environmental, or economic challenge are you trying to solve through your innovation and what is the expected impact?

There is immense power in openness as a way to power business and innovation, and many open inventions have changed the entire world. For example: The formula to create insulin, a life-saving treatment for diabetics, was patented but sold for only \$1 USD, ensuring it was openly available to all [1]; Wikipedia the volunteer-powered open and free-to-access encyclopaedia has nearly 7 million English-language articles; and the open sharing of computer programs - known as open source software - has an estimated business value of \$4.5 billion USD, according to a recent Harvard study [2].

Science underpins economic development and innovation. Despite this, *scientists often struggle to effectively share their findings with the world-at-large*, or may believe that if they do share their work, they will lose their only competitive and career advantage. I believe otherwise: science can (and should) be shared openly with other scientists, businesspeople, changemakers, and the community at large. Not only this, but I believe that sharing offers a significant strength and "special sauce" that *fuels* innovation, by reducing the wasted effort, failed experiments, and counterproductive behaviours that closed-doors science can create.

In 2019, I co-launched OLS (Open Life-Science Limited), a company limited by guarantee running an open science mentoring and training program. I'm now full-time executive director. Over this time, we successfully trained 8 cohorts of scientists. We now plan to enable others to take their work into their chosen open non-academic settings - effectively, "spinning out" our work and creating a multiplier effect for science shared openly between researchers and industry.

Expected impacts:

1. Creating an open and reusable **blueprint for academia-industry open science spin-out** collaborations. This will include documentation on the process itself, as well as trialling the blueprint with a hands-on use-case that will allow iteration based on our experience and learnings;
2. The package of **business support** offered will help OLS take advantage of commercial opportunities - not just the type of philanthropy grant-driven activities I have run before as an academic. I foresee this grant facilitating us creating stronger industry/academia partnerships - e.g. perhaps contracting with

big pharma to create open science training for antibiotic development, or other large-win contracts.

3. The **training** itself. Running an open science training cohort (including our early-stage blueprint design) within a university will create another group of academics able to share their work responsibly and carefully with the rest of the world, including enabling commercial businesses and/or new spin-outs to take advantage of their work without unneeded duplication of work.

Potential negative impacts: "Open" science does not mean radical, irresponsible transparency. We will ensure our cohort of budding open scientists are encouraged to think critically about *appropriate* and safe data-sharing. Examples: avoiding sharing ecologically sensitive data (e.g. a rare bird), patient health data, or data from historically exploited populations (e.g. indigenous peoples).

[1] <https://www.diabetes.org.uk/our-research/about-our-research/our-impact/discovery-of-insulin> (<https://www.diabetes.org.uk/our-research/about-our-research/our-impact/discovery-of-insulin>) [2] Hoffmann, Manuel, Frank Nagle, and Yanuo Zhou. "The Value of Open Source Software." (<https://www.hbs.edu/faculty/Pages/download.aspx?name=24-038.pdf>) Harvard Business School Working Paper, No. 24-038, January 2024.

7. Approach and innovation

What innovation would you develop with the award?

TL;DR: A academia-industry spin-out blueprint for open scientists, and training to deploy it.

Longer: My organisation, OLS, exists to open up scientific research, for the benefit of humanity at-large. Building on each other's shoulders allows us to collectively reach further. My team is fully women-led, comprising myself, two other directors (a third co-director recently left on maternity leave), and around 10 other staff members and contractors based in the UK, Europe, Argentina, Mexico, the USA, and Nigeria. The team and ~600 community members across 50+ countries have been doing this training for nearly five years now, with our training cohorts funded by the Chan-Zuckerberg Initiative, and more recently by NASA.

This background gives us a good idea of the types of things that work when it comes to encouraging researchers to share their work openly - but we've also learned a lot about the challenges that people face too - the kind that makes it hard to implement what they might idealistically *prefer* to be doing. We also perform scientific research on open science and community work - I myself was recently awarded my doctorate in computer science by the University of Manchester, following a study focused on the longevity of online open science communities. Similarly, Paz Bernaldo, a contractor in Argentina, is currently writing up her study on the impacts of OLS's training since 2019.

One of the foremost challenges faced by scientists we've worked with is making real-world change. Universities are often monolithic and culture change is often slow or non-existent. What this means for OLS is that once someone has trained in open science, they often ask us for advice on how to take their projects to the "next steps": effectively, we end up incubating open science spin-outs from the university, and supporting these changemakers and multipliers on our own.

The way we're supporting these people is unsustainable, however: it's an extra service involving one-on-one coaching each time a group begins the spin-out process. **What we will do:** Our spin-out process could be made more efficient by hiring an additional staff member to trial this process formally, and co-create a clear, re-usable, open guide - the "**blueprint**" we talked about in the previous question.

Whilst the need for coaching and advice is unlikely to go away completely, we hope that this blueprint will fill a niche and allow people to self-service the knowledge more easily. The blueprint would be designed specifically for UK-based scientists who wish to become independent of their universities to share their knowledge openly in industry, but without the closed-science/profit motive that is all too often expected by technology transfer offices.

Our **intellectual property policy** is, unsurprisingly, to be **as open as we can**. The blueprint would be openly-licensed for re-use, similar to our other work; see our open source website at <https://github.com/open-life-science/open-life-science.github.io> (<https://github.com/open-life-science/open-life-science.github.io>), and our training library with slide and video recordings from over 200 training sessions: <https://openlifesci.org/openseeds/library.html> (<https://openlifesci.org/openseeds/library.html>).

Appendix: Letter of support & collaboration from King's College London.

[HoD_LoS_YY_SV_Innovate.pdf \(opens in a new window\) \(/application/10135254/form/question/42272/forminput/117678/file/730634/download\)](#).

8. Plan for the award

How will you deliver the award?

This grant will be implemented by a **three-woman team** - all of whom are scientists and role models in their own right: Dr Yo Yehudi (lead applicant and Executive Director of OLS), Bethan Iley (Programme manager), and Dr Sara Villa (Resident Fellow) for the duration of the grant. Dr Villa will hold a dual position at OLS and King's College London (KCL).

WP1 - the blueprint: The blueprint work package is our primary goal for this grant: creating a step-by-step guide to allow others to re-use and re-mix our open science training, effectively spinning out independently and creating a multiplier

effect. We anticipate that in many cases, this blueprint will be re-used in a self-service way, without the need for hands-on coaching. In order to ensure that the plan is grounded in reality, we will also test this blueprint by running a trial training cohort.

WP2 - the training cohort: We will invite applications from individuals and teams at KCL to participate in an open science training cohort. We anticipate selecting 5-10 of these applicants to complete the ~4 month training course, committing 2 hours per week for the duration. They will be paired with a mentor who is an experienced open science practitioner, and attend group activities and talks on aspects of open science, community building, and DEI. KCL has committed to support additional expenses of £6,000 to pay mentors and speakers.

Risks: We have delivered eight training cohorts in the past five years; in our experience, most minor risks are manageable without severe disruption (speakers late or missing a session, cohort participant drop-out). Indeed, we've weathered some major disruptions - our first cohort began in early 2020 and rapidly had to adapt to the pandemic.

In addition to the risk mitigation strategy (attached in PDF) and Gantt timeline for project delivery, we keep our project on track and reduce our risks by regular team meetings, making reporting lines clear, and ensuring there is adequate guidance and support for timeline management and administrative tasks. Dr Villa will be the primary person responsible for delivering the content of the two work packages, with programme management support (deadlines, reporting, finance, etc.) from Bethan Iley, OLS's Finance and Operations manager. As lead applicant, Dr Yehudi will provide supervision and coaching to the two staff members.

Support package utilisation: I look forward to the opportunity to access the business support - whilst so far I am extremely proud of the ~2 million in operating funds I and my co-directors have raised over the last few years, this has been primarily via non-UK philanthropy. I believe that coaching and support could offer us pathways to collaborations with UK businesses, such as big pharma or scientific software companies. Developing a diversified and at least partly non-grant-based finance model is essential to our organisation; this opportunity looks like a strategic pathway to begin building partnerships, collaborations, and ways of working.

[Risk assessment - UKRI Innovate UK Women Innovators YY - Risk register-1.pdf \(opens in a new window\) \(/application/10135254/form/question/42273/forminput/117684/file/730646/download\).](/application/10135254/form/question/42273/forminput/117684/file/730646/download)

[Gantt - Project activity - UKRI Women in innovation - Sheet1.pdf \(opens in a new window\) \(/application/10135254/form/question/42273/forminput/117684/file/730648/download\).](/application/10135254/form/question/42273/forminput/117684/file/730648/download)

9. Added value and timeliness of the award

What added value would an injection of public funding have on the business?

OLS is nearly five years old. In 2029, by our tenth birthday, I hope to see a world that is subtly but genuinely changed. Our mission as a team is one of culture change to support responsible, ethical sharing and re-use of science worldwide. We wish to see technology transfer from universities to real-world settings flowing freely - and not only available to those based in rich countries. Many scientists do research because of passion for their subject and the world; we wish for scientists to believe that working outside academia is not a failure, nor yet an impossible path that requires skill-sets they don't have, nor battles with technology transfer offices that are determined to wring every profit-bearing penny out of their work.

To do this, we started by offering open science training, but this alone isn't enough: we quickly realised that open scientists need support to work outside of the confines of a traditional university setting. For us, it makes sense to train others, given that this is something we have so recently done ourselves in OLS. All three OLS co-founders, including me, were initially working at research institutions, and I was a research software engineer based at the Department of Genetics in Cambridge.

Timeliness: We have recently hit a crunch point, however: OLS's initial grant funding has almost come to an end, which makes it harder to sacrifice time on 1:1 coaching for our incubation initiatives. We need funding to continue it, and we need to scale and streamline the process, ideally learning how to sell it to businesses and institutes that can afford to pay. Getting funding from Innovate UK would further prove that we are not merely naive-yet-lucky academics, but also strategic entrepreneurs who are capable and ready to support other scientists in spinning out their own open science projects. We would hope, if acceptable, to share the "secrets" of the support package with our community as part of this blueprint. Despite being educated to PhD-level, to many scientists, running a business is a prospect that is mysterious, opaque, and slightly frightening.

Without this funding, we certainly would not be able to write the blueprint in the timelines described, and would continue to hunt for alternative sources of funding - but I believe that Innovate UK specifically is our best route, since it draws us closer to the "real" business world, compared to most grant bodies (Chan-Zuckerberg Initiative, NASA, Wellcome Trust, EOSC-Life) we've worked with in the past.

If we do not secure funding of some kind, continuing the incubation initiative and developing the blueprint further is likely to be a challenge. The inverse is an **opportunity:** by the time this award ends, I hope to have secured 2-3 real-world industry collaboration partnerships (contracts for service, ideally), to allow us to

spread open scientific training techniques outside of academia, or some alternative stream of income that allows us to continue supporting open scientists who wish to spin out their own innovation initiatives.

The finances of all project partners are included in this summary.

	Total costs (£)	Funding level (%)	Funding sought (£)	Contribution to project (£)	Other public sector funding (£)
OPEN LIFE SCIENCE LIMITED Organisation	74,999	100.00	74,999	0	0

Funding breakdown

	Total	Labour (£)	Overheads (£)	Materials (£)	Capital usage (£)	Subcontracting (£)	Travel and subsistence (£)	Other costs (£)
OPEN LIFE SCIENCE LIMITED	£74,999	62,001	12,400	1	0	0	597	0
Organisation								
View finances (/application/10135254/form/FINANCE)								

Terms and conditions

Award terms and conditions

Partner	Funding rules	Terms and conditions
OPEN LIFE SCIENCE LIMITED (Lead)	Subsidy control	Innovate UK - Subsidy control (/application/10135254/form/terms-and-conditions/organisation/113592/question/40910)

Supporting information

Project impact

Understanding the benefits of the projects Innovate UK supports

Partner	Status
OPEN LIFE SCIENCE LIMITED (Lead)	Complete

